

ISic1416

I.Sicily inscription 1416

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

sandstone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2015.07.23 Metcalfe

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Philosophiana

Place of origin (modern)

near Mazzarino

Provenance

Sofiana (37.31424, 14.29943)

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Gela, Museo Archeologico
Regionale di Gela, inventory 9361

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI178081

1. ²menorah²

2. Ἀττίν-

3. ις βρ ξ [σ]β-

4. ὑτερο-

5. ς ²⁶πρεσβύτερος²⁶.

6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 494019

EDCS 38000220

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Bibliography

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